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High-Mobility and Low Carrier Concentration Transparent Conducting Oxide Rear Contact for Bifacial CIGS Solar Cells

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ABSTRACT

The power conversion efficiency of bifacial Cu (In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) solar cells under rear illumination is limited by low short circuit current density (J_{sc}) values. This study investigates the potential of high-mobility, low carrier concentration transparent conducting oxides (TCOs) as transparent rear contacts (TBCs) to enhance the performance of CIGS solar cells under rear illumination. We first show by optical simulations that TCO with high carrier mobility and low carrier concentration reduces parasitic absorption and improves light coupling into the CIGS absorber, respectively. Then, CIGS solar cells are realized by implementing In₂O₃:Sn (ITO) and the higher performing In₂O₃:H (IOH) and In₂O₃:Zr (InZrO) as TBC. These TBCs significantly improve the optical coupling of rear-side illumination into the CIGS absorber, improving the rear external quantum efficiency maximum value from about 50% to above 80%. The optical transparency of IOH and InZrO TBC remains relatively unaffected after the CIGS growth process, outperforming ITO on this aspect as well. The observed poor rear EQE at short wavelength is ascribed to a strong rear interface recombination. Finally, a prospective analysis of realistically achievable rear J_{sc} gains is provided when introducing a steeper Ga gradient at the rear interface and a passivated rear contact.

1 | Introduction

Bifacial photovoltaics (PVs) have garnered significant attention and a growing market share owing to their potential to achieve higher power output per unit area as compared to conventional monofacial devices. The benefits of this technology are attractive for many applications, including building-integrated PVs [1], vertically mounted bifacial PVs [2], and agrivoltaics [3]. Unlike traditional monofacial PV, which only captures direct sunlight on its front surface, bifacial PV can also utilize reflected and diffused light on its rear surface. This dual-sided light absorption capability allows bifacial PV to achieve significantly higher energy yields, making it a highly efficient solution for solar energy generation [4].

Cu (In, Ga)Se₂ (CIGS) is one of the most promising thin-film PVs technologies for achieving high-efficiency devices with long-term efficiency at relatively low costs. The record power conversion efficiencies (PCEs) of 23.6% (rigid) and 22.2% (flexible) have been achieved in monofacial cells [5, 6]. However, the PCE of bifacial CIGS thin-film solar cells has remained at lower values, with 19.77% under front illumination and 10.89% under rear illumination [4], with a moderate bifaciality factor of about 55%. As a result, despite its great potential in various applications, the bifacial CIGS technology is mostly confined to the research and development stage.

A variety of transparent conducting oxides (TCOs) have been explored as potential transparent rear contacts (TBCs) for bifacial

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CIGS solar cells, including ZnO:Al (AZO), SnO:F (FTO), InZnO, and In₂O₃:Sn (ITO) [4, 7–23]. However, each TCO presents specific limitations: FTO suffers from reduced conductivity at elevated temperatures due to fluorine loss [24], InZnO may act as a current-blocking layer [16], and AZO and ITO often form resistive GaOx interlayers during CIGS growth [20, 24]. Recently, Yang et al. reported an approach to mitigate the formation of resistive GaOx at the rear interface by lowering the CIGS temperature growth while maintaining its quality with silver alloying [4]. Although this new synthesis strategy opens up the possibility to suppress the GaOx formation, the search continues for TBCs that combine high transparency, low resistivity, and stability under CIGS deposition conditions.

For a TCO to function effectively as a TBC, it must withstand the thermal conditions and chemical stresses from Se and Ga during absorber formation while fulfilling the following requirements: (1) establish an ohmic contact with the absorber, (2) maintain high optical transparency, and (3) exhibit low sheet resistance (R_{sheet}). Achieving the right balance among transparency, electrical conductivity, thermal/chemical stability, and interface compatibility with the CIGS absorber is essential to maximize the performance of bifacial solar cells.

In this report, we explore the electrical and optical properties of TCO under rear illumination using both experiments and numerical optical simulations to understand their effect on the optical properties of the solar cell stack. The optical simulations show that high charge carrier mobility and low carrier concentration minimize parasitic absorption in the TCO and reduce the infrared reflection losses. To experimentally demonstrate these findings, we implement three different TCO materials as TBC with varying electrical and optical properties: ITO, hydrogenated indium oxide (IOH), and zirconium-doped indium oxide (InZrO). ITO was included as a reference, given its widespread use in PVs. IOH is known for exceptionally high-mobility ($> 100 \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$) and low free carrier absorption, which have been shown to enhance NIR transparency and increase photocurrent in tandem devices [25–27]. InZrO, though less extensively studied, has demonstrated higher transparency and stability than ITO, with reports of reduced parasitic absorption and device-level current gains in tandem architectures [28–30].

We show that high transparency, low carrier concentration ITO degrades during CIGS growth, reverting to high carrier density and poor transparency, while IOH and InZrO maintain favorable properties and even improve in mobility. As a result, devices with IOH and InZrO reach rear external quantum efficiency (EQE) values above 80% at long wavelengths, significantly outperforming ITO. Finally, we provide a perspective on further enhancing bifaciality factors through optimized Ga gradients and rear-contact passivation.

2 | Experimental Procedures

2.1 | TCO Preparation

The ITO substrates (Kaivo, KV-ITO-P001) are commercially available and feature 200-nm TCO thickness on top of a SiO₂ diffusion barrier. IOH films were grown on soda lime glass

substrates at room temperature by RF sputtering of In₂O₃ targets (99.99%, 10-in. diameter, SPM AG) in an atmosphere of 0.25% of O₂ to Ar and 0.25% of H₂ to Ar ratio. The base pressure was kept below 10^{-6} mbar while the process pressure was around 3×10^{-3} mbar. The applied sputter power density was 0.5 W/cm². The IOH deposition conditions were adapted from previous optimization work within our group [25]. The thickness of IOH films was ~650 nm for solar cell fabrication. Approximately 400 nm of InZrO with sheet resistance around 48 Ω/sq is deposited at room temperature from a 4-in. (98% In₂O₃ + 2% ZrO) target with power density of 0.93 W/cm² and working pressure of 3 mbar with 1.4% of O₂ to Ar ratio. These deposition conditions yield low carrier concentration films with high optical transparency and sufficient electrical conductivity, as detailed in the referenced work [28].

2.2 | Solar Cell Fabrication

CIGS absorbers were grown following a three-stage co-evaporation process on ITO, IOH, and InZrO TBC. During the first stage of deposition, silver is co-evaporated along with indium (In), gallium (Ga), and selenium (Se), $[\text{Ag}]/([\text{Ag}] + [\text{Cu}])$ (AAC) ~ 0.02. The substrate temperature during the second and third stages was varied as indicated in the manuscript (300°C, 330°C, and 360°C nominal value). The nominal temperature is measured by a thermocouple placed above the sample. The actual temperature value is about 100°C higher than the nominal one and may depend on the sample rear contact emissivity and infrared optical properties. The absorbers processed at 330°C and 360°C were deposited in the same respective CIGS deposition runs, while the 300°C samples were processed in different runs yet with similar nominal parameters. The depositions were finished with NaF and RbF post-deposition treatments. A detailed description of the growth conditions can be found in [31]. The absorber composition was determined by X-ray fluorescence, and the $[\text{Ga}]/([\text{Ga}] + [\text{In}])$ (GGI) and $[\text{Cu}]/([\text{Ga}] + [\text{In}])$ (CGI) values were calculated from the Cu, Ga, and Se K_α lines according to [16]. The absorbers were covered by a 35-nm CdS buffer layer deposited in a chemical bath. The transparent window consists of 70-nm intrinsic ZnO and 200-nm Al-doped ZnO deposited by RF sputtering using a ZnO:Al₂O₃ (98:2 wt%) target. The cells were finished with electron beam evaporated Ni/Al grids. Finally, cells with an area of about 0.55 cm² were defined by mechanical scribing. Each substrate contained 18 individual solar cells. Unless otherwise stated, all reported device characteristics for a given TCO correspond to measurements across these 18 solar cells.

2.3 | Characterization Methods

Current–voltage (J–V) characteristics were measured in a four-contact mode at standard test conditions (1000 Wm⁻², 25°C, in the air) using a Keithley 2400 source meter. A class ABA solar simulator was used to simulate the AM 1.5G spectrum. A chopped white light source (900 W halogen lamp) with a LOT MSH-300 monochromator was used to record EQE spectra. A halogen light bias with about 0.2 sun intensity was applied during the measurement. Certified Si and Ge cells were used for calibration. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) measurements were done on a Hitachi S-4800 electron microscope.

Transmission (T) and reflection (R) spectra were acquired using an ultraviolet–visible–near infrared spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-3600) equipped with an integrating sphere. Compositional depth profiles were measured by SIMS on complete CIGS solar cells. The primary beam was 25 keV Bi⁺ with a total current of 0.4 pA and a raster size of 100 × 100 μm². The sputtering beam was 650 nA, 2 keV O₂⁺ with an on-sample area of 300 × 300 μm². Room temperature Hall-effect measurements were performed on an Ecopia (HMS3000) Hall-effect system using a 0.58 T magnetic field. Connections of indium metal for electrical measurements were made by ultrasonic soldering.

3 | Results and Discussion

3.1 | An Ideal TBC for Bifacial Application

The major bottleneck to the performance of a bifacial CIGS solar cell under rear illumination is the low short circuit current density (J_{sc}). To minimize the J_{sc} losses arising from the TBC, it is relevant to provide guidelines regarding the desired TCO electrical and optical properties so as to minimize the reflectance and absorption losses under rear illumination. Therefore, we performed transfer matrix method (TMM) optical simulations of the relevant layer stack SLG/TCO/CIGS illuminated through the glass, as shown in Figure 1. The open-source python *tmm* package was used for the calculations [32, 33] with an in-house wrapper. The complex refractive indices of SLG and CIGS are taken from [34] the latter consisting of composition (GGI:0.28, CGI:0.86) and thickness (2 μm). The refractive index *n* of the TCO model used in the simulation was calculated using the Reffit software [35]. The simplified TCO model consists of a ε_∞ = 4 value corresponding to refractive index *n* = 2 and a Drude–Lorentz oscillator modelling the free carrier absorption with values calculated from optical mobility μ and free carrier concentration *N* [36]:

$$\mu = e\tau/m^* \quad (1)$$

$$N = \frac{\epsilon_0 m^* \omega_p^2}{e^2} \quad (2)$$

where *e* is the electron charge, τ is the relaxation time or scattering time of carriers, *m*^{*} = 0.28 *m*₀ [37] is the effective mass of charge carriers, ε₀ is the permittivity of free space, and ω_{*p*} is the plasma frequency. We consider mobility μ values of 30 and 90 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ and carrier concentration 1 × 10²⁰, 4 × 10²⁰, and 1 × 10²¹ cm⁻³, with corresponding refractive index spectra reported in Figure S1. We note that the simulations can only be analyzed above 500-nm wavelength, as the simplified TCO optical model does not account for the bandgap. To achieve a sheet resistance of 10 Ω/sq in each case, the thickness of TCO was adjusted accordingly, following the relationship

$$R_{sheet} = 1 / e\mu Nd \quad (3)$$

where *R*_{sheet} is the sheet resistance, *e* the electron charge, and *d* the TCO film thickness.

The simulation results are displayed in Figure 1. On the one hand, Figure 1a shows that TCOs with low mobility (μ ≤ 30 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹) lead to high parasitic absorption, irrespective of the carrier concentration, as the layer thickness is adapted to yield the desired 10 Ω/sq sheet resistance value. Therefore, a mobility of 30 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ leads to nonnegligible absorption losses in the TCO (or alternatively in a reduced device FF due to high contact sheet resistance if the TCO layer thickness is reduced). Besides, a low device rear reflectance can be achieved with low carrier concentration (≤ 4 × 10²⁰ cm⁻³). On the other hand, a high-mobility TCO (here 90 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹) offers lower parasitic absorption and higher optical coupling into the CIGS layer (Figure 1b). Similar to low-mobility TCO, low carrier concentration also reduces the reflectance losses. Moreover, thinner films can be used to achieve low sheet resistance (≤ 10 Ω/sq). Therefore, to minimize the TBC losses, one should target high-mobility and low carrier concentration TCOs.

FIGURE 1 | Comparison of TMM simulated reflectance and absorption losses in the TCO rear contact with (a) low TCO mobility: 30 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹ and (b) high TCO mobility: 90 cm²V⁻¹s⁻¹. The dashed line indicates the optical absorption in the CIGS layer (equal to EQE in case all photocarriers were collected), while the shaded region indicates absorption in TCO. The legends indicate the TCO carrier concentration (cm⁻³) and thickness (nm). The layer structure is SLG/TCO/CIGS, with the TCO thickness adjusted to obtain 10 Ω/sq sheet resistance in each case.

We stress that the Fresnel reflection at the TCO/CIGS interface becomes large at high TCO carrier concentration, due to the contrast of refractive index with CIGS (about $n=2.8$), combined with the TCO low n and high k values. This large reflection does not occur with the commonly measured TCO/glass test samples, where the TCO may even act as an antireflecting coating.

In addition to the above optical considerations, chemical stability under the demanding environment of CIGS deposition (high process temperature, Se ambient) is equally important. The optical properties of TBC should not degrade after the CIGS deposition process, and the electrical properties should approach the desired values.

3.2 | ITO: Most Popular TBC

ITO is the most widely used TBC for bifacial CIGS solar cells, although it typically suffers from high carrier concentration ($\geq 1 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and low mobility ($< 30 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Annealing in air is often applied to TCOs to tune their electrical and optical properties [38–40]. During this process, oxygen incorporation reduces the free carrier concentration by suppressing donor activation, leading to improved infrared transparency. We therefore investigated how ITO responds to annealing and subsequent CIGS growth.

We used commercial ITO with a high carrier concentration ($\geq 1 \times 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and mobility less than $30 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and annealed them at 300°C , 400°C , and 500°C for 20 min in air in a muffle furnace. ITO films annealed at 500°C showed improved long-wavelength transmittance (Figure S2), associated with a reduced carrier concentration and increased R_{sheet} (Table S1). This effect is likely due to oxygen vacancy filling during annealing [41, 42]. In contrast, 300°C annealing had minimal effect on the properties of ITO; therefore, devices were fabricated on pristine ITO, ITO annealed at 400°C , and ITO annealed at 500°C .

Figure 2a shows the J–V curves for CIGS solar cells on ITO: pristine (not annealed), ITO annealed at 400°C (ITO:400), and ITO annealed at 500°C (ITO:500). Under front illumination, devices fabricated on pristine and 400°C -annealed ITO reached efficiencies of $\sim 15\%$, while the devices on 500°C -annealed ITO exhibited mild current-blocking behavior under both front and rear illumination. The detailed PV parameters reported in Figure S3 indicate that the device efficiency of ITO:500 is limited by FF loss. Under front illumination, all devices showed similar EQE (Figure 2b). Under rear illumination, however, EQE dropped markedly, particularly beyond 900 nm , due to reflection losses and parasitic absorption in ITO. At short wavelengths, additional losses arise from recombination at the ITO/CIGS interface, where high-energy photons absorbed near the rear interface exhibit low collection efficiency. A more detailed discussion of the rear EQE is provided in the upcoming sections.

FIGURE 2 | (a) I–V characteristics and (b) EQE spectra under front (solid) and rear (dashed) illumination for solar cells on ITO rear contact, pristine (not annealed) or air annealed at 400°C and 500°C before CIGS deposition. The 1-R curve is shown for sample ITO:pristine (c) transmittance and (d) reflectance of ITO/SLG stacks layer before CIGS deposition and after CIGS mechanical removal.

TABLE 1 | Electrical properties (mobility, carrier concentration, and sheet resistance) of ITO films before CIGS deposition and after mechanical removal of CIGS.

Substrate	Mobility ($\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)		CC (cm^{-3})		R_{sheet} (Ω/sq)	
	Before CIGS	After CIGS	Before CIGS	After CIGS	Before CIGS	After CIGS
ITO:pristine	27	23	2.1×10^{21}	1.8×10^{21}	8	8
ITO:400	31	25	1.1×10^{21}	1.7×10^{21}	9	8
ITO:500	33	26	4.1×10^{20}	1.7×10^{21}	23	7

Note: The instrument measurement uncertainty is estimated at $\pm 5.5\%$ (mobility), $\pm 3.9\%$ (CC), and $\pm 2.5\%$ (R_{sheet}).

We also measured the transmittance and reflectance of ITO films after mechanical removal of the CIGS and window layers. The comparison of transmittance and reflectance of ITO films before and after CIGS removal is shown in Figure 2c and Figure 2d, respectively. The results show that the annealing-induced improvements in ITO transparency were lost as all ITO samples displayed nearly identical transmittance and reflectance spectra after CIGS growth. Hall measurements conducted on these ITO films are reported in Table 1. The instrument measurement uncertainty values listed in the caption were calculated from the equipment specifications provided by the manufacturer. Process repeatability is estimated to be within $\pm 25\%$ for the reported electrical properties under identical processing, though this assessment is based on a few repeats only. These measurements further confirmed that the electrical properties of annealed ITO reverted to those of pristine ITO after CIGS growth. Notably, R_{sheet} of the 500°C sample dropped from $>20\Omega/\text{sq}$ before growth to $<10\Omega/\text{sq}$ afterward, matching the other ITO films.

In summary, while air annealing temporarily improves ITO properties, the CIGS deposition process negates these effects, likely through mechanisms analogous to high-temperature vacuum annealing or some form of doping during CIGS growth. Because ITO reverts to its initial high carrier concentration, it does not fulfill the requirements for an efficient TBC in bifacial CIGS under our deposition conditions. This highlights the need for alternative materials with higher mobility and lower carrier concentration for use as a transparent back contact.

3.3 | IOH and InZrO: Potential Candidates for TBC

Based on the simulation criteria of high-mobility and low carrier concentration, we investigated IOH and InZrO as alternatives to ITO. Both materials are known for their high transparency and reduced parasitic absorption compared to ITO.

Figure S4 shows their transmittance and reflectance spectra, while Table S2 summarizes the electrical properties. Before CIGS growth, IOH and InZrO already exhibit higher transparency and lower NIR reflectance than ITO. Their carrier concentrations lie within the optimal range identified in the simulations (Figure 1), although mobilities are lower than the desired values, particularly for InZrO. In addition, before CIGS deposition, InZrO shows a relatively high sheet resistance ($\sim 50\Omega/\text{sq}$), above the target value of $10\Omega/\text{sq}$.

3.4 | Device Performance Under Front Illumination

Bifacial CIGS solar cells were fabricated by using ITO, IOH, and InZrO TBCs at nominal substrate temperatures (T_{sub}) of 300°C, 330°C, and 360°C during the second and third CIGS deposition stages. Representative J–V curves are shown in Figure 3a–c and corresponding EQE spectra in Figure 3d–f. All TCOs successfully formed an ohmic rear contact with the absorber, except for ITO at 360°C (Figure 3a), which exhibited mild blocking behavior, limiting the FF of the device. This is attributed to GaOx formation at the ITO/CIGS interface which is highly resistive [4, 20, 21]. By contrast, IOH and InZrO maintained suitable ohmic contacts even at the highest 360°C T_{sub} (actual value estimated to $\sim 450^\circ\text{C}$).

Statistical I–V characterization results for both front and rear illumination are presented in Figure 4. We first discuss the front-side illumination data. The Voc shows significant variation (exceeding 100 mV) across different samples, including absorbers processed in the same run on different TBCs (330°C and 360°C series). The morphology of CIGS absorber improves with higher substrate temperature and appears largely independent of the TBC material. Cross-sectional SEM images (Figure S5) reveal poor morphologies at 300°C, which improve considerably at higher temperatures. Similarly, the low-energy exponential decay (E_{u}) extracted from EQE spectra (Figure S6) decreases with increasing T_{sub} and remains at a reasonable level below 20 meV. A lower E_{u} reflects fewer band-tail states and reduced disorder, which should, in principle, yield higher Voc [43–45]. Based on morphology and tail states alone, an increase in Voc with rising T_{sub} would be expected regardless of TBC. However, the observed Voc variations are larger than anticipated and do not follow this trend. These variations are, nevertheless, consistent with PLQY and TRPL lifetime measurements on CdS-covered samples. The Voc loss estimates derived from PLQY and TRPL lifetimes are summarized in Table S3 and show good agreement with those obtained from JV curves. The ΔVoc term derived from PLQY represents the absolute nonradiative Voc loss with respect to the radiative limit, whereas the δVoc terms extracted from JV, PLQY, and TRPL are in comparison to the selected reference sample. The voltage implied by PLQY measurements is in excellent agreement with JV values, whereas the TRPL decay times suggest comparable yet somewhat smaller voltage variations. The increased nonradiative recombination in the absorber bulk or at the front interface is captured by PLQY and (for the most part) TRPL decay times, for ITO_330C, InZrO_330C, and InZrO_360C.

FIGURE 3 | I-V curves under front illumination of bifacial CIGS solar cells grown at different nominal substrate temperatures (300°C, 330°C, and 360°C), on (a) ITO, (b) IOH, and (c) InZrO transparent rear contacts. EQE spectra for the same solar cells on (d) ITO, (e) IOH, and (f) InZrO TBC, along with cell front reflectance of the 300°C series.

FIGURE 4 | Photovoltaic parameters for solar cells with ITO, IOH, and InZrO transparent rear contact grown at different T_{sub} under front (bright colors, left-shifted) and rear illumination (shaded colors, right-shifted). One sample containing 18 cells was fabricated for each condition, and the data of individual cells are shown as gray dots.

Jsc values were consistent across TBCs and T_{sub} , in line with the similar EQE responses (Figure 3d–f). In contrast, FF was strongly affected by the rear contact. ITO devices showed a clear FF loss with increasing T_{sub} , explained by the formation of a resistive GaOx layer. Series resistance (R_s) values increased from $\sim 2 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$ (300°C) to $5.5 \Omega\text{-cm}^2$ (360°C , Figure S7). IOH and InZrO devices maintained low R_s across all conditions, consistent with the absence of GaOx interlayer, or of a very thin one. In the case of InZrO, a FF loss at high T_{sub} was observed, although the underlying cause remains unclear. We tentatively associate it with the decrease in V_{oc} rather than contact resistance.

Overall, IOH devices showed the most robust behavior, with efficiencies consistently increasing with T_{sub} , reaching 17.6% under front illumination without antireflective coating (and 7.6% under rear, discussed below). The efficiency evolution for ITO and InZrO was less systematic, reflecting their sensitivity to interfacial or bulk recombination effects.

3.5 | Device Performance Under Rear Illumination

Representative J–V curves under rear illumination are shown in Figure 5a–c, with statistical results in Figure 4 (faded colors). Compared to front illumination, performance is primarily limited by Jsc, which drops to about one-third of its value under front illumination. V_{oc} decreases by $\sim 50\text{mV}$ for all samples, largely due to the reduced photocurrent. FF values are similar or slightly improved under rear illumination, possibly as a result of the reduced carrier concentration reaching the pn junction, which tends to result in diode ideality factors and reverse saturation currents values closer to the better values obtained in the dark.

The results of EQE measurements under rear illumination are shown in Figure 5d–f. Corresponding TCO parasitic absorption (shaded area) and cell rear reflectance (1-R) of the respective

300°C sample are also presented. At short wavelengths, EQE is suppressed for all TBCs by recombination at the rear interface. With increasing wavelength, EQE rises as carriers are generated deeper in the absorber and collection probability improves. IOH devices show some improvement at short wavelengths with higher T_{sub} , possibly reflecting better absorber quality at the rear interface compared to 300°C samples. At long wavelengths ($> 900\text{nm}$), IOH_330C and IOH_360C show a slight shift of the EQE maximum toward shorter wavelengths relative to IOH_300C, which we attribute to stronger rear Ga gradients (Figure S8). A higher Ga content increases the rear bandgap, allows more photon absorption deep in the absorber, and shifts the EQE curve maximum to shorter wavelengths. Bandgap grading can assist in providing effective passivation of photons absorbed far from the rear interface and improving collection [4, 46, 47].

Overall, EQE maxima are strongly influenced by the TCO properties. ITO devices are limited by reflection losses and parasitic absorption due to high carrier concentration and low mobility, consistent with the simulations in Figure 1. In contrast, IOH and InZrO achieve EQE maxima $\geq 80\%$ by mitigating both reflection and absorption losses.

To further probe TCO stability, transmittance, reflectance, and Hall measurements were performed after mechanically removing the CIGS absorber (Figure 6, Table 2). The overall transmittance of the TCO/glass stack decreases after CIGS deposition, partly due to absorption and light scattering from residual CIGS particles left on the TCO substrate following mechanical removal (see Figure S9). While IOH and InZrO largely retained their transparency, ITO showed a substantial loss across the spectrum, indicating material degradation. Despite different initial values of R_{sheet} , all TCOs reach the desired sheet resistance of $\sim 10 \Omega/\text{sq}$ after CIGS deposition. The change in sheet resistance is particularly striking for InZrO, where R_{sheet} decreases from $\sim 50 \Omega/\text{sq}$ before CIGS growth to $\leq 10 \Omega/\text{sq}$ afterward. The CIGS growth process acts as an

FIGURE 5 | J–V curves of bifacial CIGS solar cells with (a) ITO, (b) IOH, and (c) InZrO transparent rear contact grown at 300°C , 330°C , and 360°C nominal substrate temperature, under rear illumination. (d–f) EQE spectra of the corresponding cells, together with (1-R) reflectance loss (corresponding 300°C sample), and estimated absorption loss in the rear TCO measured after delamination of the CIGS absorber.

FIGURE 6 | Transmittance and reflectance of (a) ITO, (b) IOH, and (c) InZrO on glass slabs before CIGS deposition (pristine), and after mechanical removal of CIGS and window layers.

TABLE 2 | Electrical properties (mobility, carrier concentration, and sheet resistance) of ITO, IOH, and InZrO films before CIGS deposition and after mechanical removal of CIGS and window layers.

Substrate	Mobility ($\text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$)		CC (cm^{-3})		R_{sheet} (Ω/sq)	
	Before CIGS	After CIGS	Before CIGS	After CIGS	Before CIGS	After CIGS
ITO_300C	27	23	2.1×10^{21}	1.8×10^{21}	8	8
ITO_330C		25		1.6×10^{21}		8
ITO_360C		22		1.9×10^{21}		8
IOH_300C	49	83	3.5×10^{20}	1.5×10^{20}	6	12
IOH_330C		95		9.2×10^{19}		11
IOH_360C		93		6.9×10^{19}		15
InZrO_300C	27	52	1.2×10^{20}	3.0×10^{20}	48	10
InZrO_330C		52		3.0×10^{20}		10
InZrO_360C		54		3.8×10^{20}		8

Note: Instrument-based measurement uncertainty is estimated at $\pm 5.5\%$ (Mobility), $\pm 3.9\%$ (CC), and $\pm 2.5\%$ (R_{sheet}).

annealing step for IOH and InZrO, enhancing their mobilities to ~ 90 and $\sim 50 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$, respectively. IOH carrier concentration decreased progressively with T_{sub} , whereas InZrO concentration increased from $\sim 1.2 \times 10^{20}$ to $\sim 3 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. These results show that the CIGS thermal process effectively anneals IOH and InZrO, enhancing mobility, while ITO remains largely unchanged and less stable optically.

The improvements in rear EQE obtained with IOH and InZrO, despite all TCOs exhibiting similar sheet resistances after CIGS growth, highlight the decisive role of optical transparency over lateral conduction. Comparable trends have been documented in earlier studies, where high-mobility TCOs were shown to significantly suppress free carrier absorption relative to ITO. For IOH, Jiang et al. reported mobilities up to $\sim 129 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ and $\sim 82\%$ average transmittance between 820 and 1300 nm, yielding an $\sim 1.4 \text{ mAcm}^{-2}$ current gain versus InZnO in tandem devices [25]. Battaglia et al. further showed $\sim 1.2 \text{ mAcm}^{-2}$ current improvement in micromorph Si cells when replacing ITO with IOH, directly linked to reduced NIR absorption [26]. For InZrO, Aydin et al. demonstrated mobilities of $\sim 77\text{--}87 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ with parasitic absorption reduced to $\sim 5\%$ (compared to $\sim 10\%$ for ITO) across 250–2500 nm, translating to a 3.5 mAcm^{-2} current gain and efficiency increase from 23.3% to 26.2% in four-terminal tandems [28]. Another study reveals that InZrO maintains high transparency ($> 85\%$ in NIR) and low sheet resistance ($\sim 15 \Omega/\text{sq}$)

even after thermal processing, outperforming ITO, which suffers increased absorption and resistivity under the same conditions [30]. Together with our results Figure 5d–f, these studies confirm that employing high mobility, low carrier concentration TCOs such as IOH and InZrO effectively reduces parasitic absorption and reflection, thereby enhancing rear-illumination EQE compared to ITO.

3.6 | Toward High Bifaciality Factors

Under rear illumination, our devices show little change in FF, while the V_{oc} loss mainly reflects the reduced J_{sc} . Thus, improving rear-side J_{sc} is the key challenge for achieving high bifaciality factors in CIGS. Implementing high-mobility TCOs such as IOH and InZrO already mitigates reflection and parasitic absorption losses, enabling EQE maxima above 80% in the NIR (Figure 5e,f). Further improvement in the bifaciality factor will require additional absorber and rear-contact engineering, which we have schematically illustrated in Figure 7.

One promising route is optimization of the Ga gradient in the CIGS layer. A high rear bandgap and steep Ga gradient offer a strong gradient in the electrical potential, which assists the drift of the electron minority carriers generated at or near the rear interface toward the pn junction, resulting in reduced

FIGURE 7 | Strategies to further improve the EQE response under rear illumination. The starting points correspond to the devices obtained on ITO and IOH. An improved Ga gradient improves the spectral response in the visible [4]. Passivated contact allows good spectral response also in the blue region of the spectrum.

recombination losses and improved collection efficiency. Based on Ref. [4], such an optimized profile could increase rear J_{sc} from ~ 14 to ~ 29 mAcm^{-2} under rear illumination. With front J_{sc} values near 37 mAcm^{-2} , bifaciality factors above 75% may be achieved with optimized compositional gradients.

Rear-contact passivation provides another strategy, which can help in reducing the surface recombination and improving the spectral response. Such a passivating effect can be induced by, for example, reducing the density of defects and/or by creating an additional electrical field using, for example, a dielectric layer with fixed charges to repel the minority carrier away from the rear contact. Successful implementation of such a passivation layer also alleviates or even removes altogether the requirement for a high and steep compositional gradient inside the CIGS absorber. Passivation layer strategies may further improve the spectral response at short wavelength and surpass 30 mAcm^{-2} and bifaciality factors of or above 90%.

Alternative approaches include using thinner, lower-doped absorbers, so that the space-charge region extends across the entire absorber thickness, similar to perovskite devices. However, to maintain high V_{oc} in such architectures, well-passivated contacts remain essential, since V_{oc} losses are more critical in the relatively low-bandgap CIGS absorber [48–50].

Finally, we note that the estimates in Figure 7 do not account for optical management strategies (e.g., light trapping or advanced TCO/texturing). They should therefore be considered as indicative rather than absolute limits. Overall, a combination of optimized Ga grading, rear-contact passivation, and improved optical management could enable CIGS bifacial devices with bifaciality factors approaching 90%.

4 | Conclusion

The present study highlights the TCO electrical and optical properties optimal for their implementation as a TBC in

high-performance bifacial CIGS solar cells, in a planar configuration where a low TCO sheet resistance of about $10\ \Omega/\text{sq}$ is desired to mitigate the electrical transport losses due to lateral charge transport.

Optical TMM simulations suggest that high carrier mobility (ideally above $50\ \text{cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) and low carrier concentration (ideally below $4 \times 10^{20}\ \text{cm}^{-3}$) are needed to reduce the TCO optical parasitic absorption and the reflectance at the TCO/CIGS optical interface, respectively. We note that high carrier densities not only induce free carrier absorption but also lower the real part of the refractive index, in turn increasing the reflectance at the TCO/CIGS interface. Measuring transmittance only on TCO/glass slabs may lead to overlooking the severity of the TCO/CIGS interface reflectance.

ITO rear contacts are commonly used as TBC for CIGS, despite the high carrier concentration typically above $1 \times 10^{21}\ \text{cm}^{-3}$. We could reduce the carrier concentration of commercial ITO layers by thermal air annealing. However, upon CIGS deposition, the ITO's electrical and optical properties reverted to the initial nonoptimal starting point, limiting the EQE under rear illumination.

Bifacial CIGS devices were fabricated to validate the predictions, comparing ITO to the high-mobility alternatives IOH and InZrO. All TCO layers featured about $10\ \Omega/\text{sq}$ sheet resistance after CIGS deposition and modification of their carrier concentration and mobility. Further, all three also formed ohmic contact to the CIGS absorber, with a minor resistive behavior appearing for ITO at the highest investigated process temperature, demonstrating suitable chemical and thermal stability for compatibility with the CIGS co-evaporation process.

We assess that the devices performed about similarly under front illumination, with up to 17.6% efficiency without anti-reflecting coating. However, large but not systematic variations in V_{oc} are observed, the origin of which has not yet been elucidated. Under rear illumination, the device performance is reduced by low J_{sc} values and marginally by the corresponding V_{oc} reduction. The rear EQE, especially at long wavelength, benefits from high-mobility and low carrier concentration TCO alternatives, with EQE maximum values above 80% at long wavelength. This confirms the prediction of the optical simulations. The reduced EQE at short wavelength is attributed to nonoptimal Ga gradient in the investigated CIGS absorbers.

Better suited compositional gradients with higher bandgap value at the rear and steeper gradients have already been reported with very similar deposition process conditions. Implementation of such gradients should allow pushing the performance limits of bifacial CIGS under rear illumination, tentatively close to 80% bifaciality factor, with unchanged high performance under front illumination. Pathways for further improvements are discussed.

While this study specifically targets bifacial CIGS solar cells, the optical requirements may be similar for other thin-film technologies for their use as stand-alone bifacial applications or as semi-transparent devices for tandem device approaches.

Author Contributions

Nisika Nisika: conceptualization, methodology, validation, investigation, data curation, writing – original draft, writing – review and editing, visualization. **Shiro Nishiwaki:** conceptualization, methodology, validation, investigation, data curation, writing – review and editing, visualization. **Ceren Mitmit:** methodology, validation, investigation, data curation, writing – review and editing. **Matteo De Marzi:** methodology, validation, investigation, writing – review and editing. **Kerem Artuk:** methodology, validation, investigation, writing – review and editing. **Christian M. Wolff:** methodology, validation, investigation, writing – review and editing. **Romain Carron:** conceptualization, methodology, validation, writing – review and editing, supervision, project administration, funding acquisition.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

We are willing to share the data used in the manuscript to create the figures and tables.

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Supporting Information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section. **Figure S1:** Real (n) and imaginary part (k) (dashed lines) of refractive index for TCO with different electrical properties. **Figure S2:** Transmittance (T%) and reflectance (R%) of ITO films on glass substrate before and after air annealing at 300°C, 400°C, and 500°C for 20 min. **Table S1:** Electrical parameters of ITO films before and after air annealing at different temperatures. Instrument-based measurement uncertainty is estimated at ± 5.5% (Mobility), ± 3.9% (CC), and ± 2.5% (Rsheet). **Figure S3:** PV performance parameters for ITO devices with pre-annealing in air before CIGS deposition at 400°C and 500°C under front (bright box plots) illumination and rear (shaded box plots) illumination. For each condition, one sample containing 18 cells was fabricated, and the data of individual cells are shown as gray dots. **Figure S4:** Transmittance (T%) and reflectance (R%) spectra of ITO, IOH, and InZrO films before CIGS deposition. **Table S2:** Electrical properties of ITO, IOH, and InZrO films before CIGS deposition. Instrument-based measurement uncertainty is estimated at ± 5.5% (Mobility), ± 3.9% (CC), and ± 2.5% (Rsheet). **Figure S5:** Cross-sectional SEM images of ITO, IOH, and InZrO samples grown at 300°C, 330°C, and 360°C substrate temperature. **Figure S6:** Urbach energy, Eu, (calculated from EQE spectra) for ITO, IOH, and InZrO solar cells with CIGS absorber grown at 300°C, 330°C, and 360°C substrate temperature. Error bars represent the standard deviation of Eu values calculated from EQE spectra measured on 4 different solar

cells from the same TCO substrate. **Table S3:** Complementary VOC-loss analysis based on PLQY and effective lifetime (τ_{eff}) using Equations (1) and (2) (given below). **Figure S7:** Change in series resistance of ITO, IOH, and InZrO solar cells with increase in substrate temperature. Each data point represents average value of R_s for all samples. Error bars are not provided since the dataset corresponds to a single representative sample. **Figure S8:** GGI profiles of absorbers grown at 300°C and 360°C substrate temperature on IOH TBC. **Figure S9:** TCO after mechanical removal of CIGS and top window layer.